

Studies on Benzocoumarins. Part-I

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Angularly fused benzocoumarins across 5,6 and 7,8 positions have been of synthetic¹ and spectroscopic interest². 3-Aryl-5,6-benzocoumarins were synthesised as potential antagonists of sex hormones and plant growth inhibitors³. Further, sulphonamides containing coumarin moiety have been reported as possible antimicrobials⁴, optical brighteners⁵, antidiabetic⁶ and antitubercular agents⁷. Coumarinyl-sulphonamidothiazoles have been found to inhibit the growth of *Alternaria solani* and the growth of mustard seed germination⁸. In the light of these observations the present study reports synthesis (Scheme 1) and spectral and antimicrobial properties of the two regioisomeric, angularly fused benzocoumarinyl sulphonamides 3 and 6

ved around 1700 cm^{-1} . Further, these were converted to the corresponding sulphonamides 3 and 6 by reacting them with arylsulphonylchlorides^{10,11} in benzene in presence of triethylamine (Table 1). The 4-acetamidosalphonamide (3c) was hydrolysed to the corresponding 4-aminosalphonamide (3d) under mildly acidic conditions. Compound 3d exhibited N—H anti-symmetric and NH symmetric stretching vibrations at 3500 and 3392 cm^{-1} respectively. The calculated value¹² for the latter (3411 cm^{-1}) also supports this assignment. The band at 3276 cm^{-1} was assigned to sulphonamide NH stretching. The pmr spectrum of 3b showed a three proton singlet at $\delta 2.2$ due to CH_3 protons. The methylene protons were found to resonate at $\delta 4.00$. The coumarin 3-proton was observed at δ

7,8-Benzo-4-bromomethylcoumarin (1) and 5,6-benzo-4-bromomethylcoumarin (4) were prepared by the reaction of 1- and 2-naphthols with 4-bromoethylacetoacetate as reported in the literature⁹. These were converted to the corresponding amine hydrochlorides 2 and 5 by acid hydrolysis of their hexamine adducts. Compounds 2 and 5 exhibited NH stretching vibrations in the region of $2600\text{--}2800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and CO stretching vibrations were obser-

ved around 1700 cm^{-1} . The aromatic multiplet was seen at $\delta 6.6\text{--}7.5$.

Antimicrobial activity: The sulphonamides 3 and 6 were screened against *B. aureus*, *S. aureus* and *E. coli* by the agar plate technique by dissolving the compounds in DMF ($200\text{ }\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$). Compounds 3c and 3f showed partial inhibition of *S. aureus* and *B. aureus* and were inactive against *E.*

coli. Compounds 6a, 6c and 6d also showed partial inhibition of *S. aureus* and *E. coli* but were inactive against *B. aureus*. Antifungal activity was tested against *A. niger* and *C. albicans* and the activity was measured by the turbidity method at 660 nm. Compounds 3e and 6a showed considerable inhibition of *A. niger* while 3b, 3c and 3f showed partial inhibition. All the compounds were inactive against *C. albicans*.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3 AND 6*

Compd. no.	R	M.p.** °C	ν_{\max} (cm ⁻¹)		
			NH	CO	SO
3a	H	219 ^b	3 250	1 720	1 390, 1 342, 1 382, 1 316
b	4-CH ₃	195 ^b	3 284	1 716	1 380, 1 322
c	4-NHCOCH ₃	261 ^a	3 332, 3 310	1 694	1 384, 1 306
d	4-NH ₂	265 ^b	3 500, 3 392, 3 276	1 720	1 384, 1 306
e	4-Br	230 ^a	3 304	1 710	1 390, 1 348
f	2,5-Br	271 ^a	3 244	1 706	1 380, 1 332
6a	H	227 ^a	3 312	1 724	1 322
b	4-CH ₃	188 ^a	3 268	1 724	1 320
c	4-NHCOCH ₃	225 ^a	3 388, 3 214	1 719	1 335
d	2,5-Br	201 ^b	3 188	1 694	1 368, 1 336

*All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

**Crystallised from : ^aacetic acid or dilute acetic acid ;
^bethanol.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 257 spectrophotometer at Karnatak University, and pmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a 60 MHz instrument.

Benzo-4-aminomethylcoumarin hydrochlorides (2 and 5): To hexamine (2.89 g, 0.02 mol) taken in dry chloroform (25 ml), was added a clear solution of benzo-4-bromomethylcoumarin (5.78 g, 0.02 mol) in dry chloroform (25 ml) with stirring. The resulting mixture was stirred at room temperature for 3 h when the hexamine adduct was found to separate. It was filtered off, washed with dry chloroform and stirred with a solution of concentrated HCl (15 ml) and ethanol (20 ml) at room temperature for 3 h. The mixture was then cooled, filtered, the resulting solid washed with ethanol

and dry ether to obtain colourless amine hydrochloride : 2 (90%), m.p. 264° (Found : C, 64.42; H, 4.74; N, 5.21. C₁₄H₁₂NO₂Cl requires : C, 64.24; H, 4.58; N, 5.35%); ν_{\max} 5 (85%), m.p. 203° (Found : C, 64.12; H, 4.77; N, 5.56. C₁₄H₁₂NO₂Cl requires : C, 64.24; H, 4.58; N, 5.35%).

Benzo-4-sulphonamidomethylcoumarins (3 and 6).
General method: A mixture of a benzo-4-aminomethylcoumarin hydrochloride (0.01 mol), triethylamine (2 ml, 0.02 mol) and dry benzene (50 ml) was stirred for 30 min at room temperature. To it an arylsulphonylchloride was added and the mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 10 h. Benzene was then distilled off, the residue treated with hot water, filtered and the resulting solid was recrystallised from a suitable solvent (Table 1), yield 60–85%.

Hydrolysis of 4-p-acetamidobenzene-sulphonamidomethyl benzocoumarin (3c): A mixture of 3c (800 mg) and HCl (1 : 1; 15 ml) was gently boiled under reflux for 2 h. The acidic solution was cooled to room temperature and neutralised with sodium bicarbonate. The separated solid was recrystallised from ethanol to get 3d (Table 1).

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